

Cosmic-Ray-Induced Chemical Processes in CH₃OH, CH₃NH₂, and CH₃OH:CH₃NH₂ Ices

Conventional and Novel IR Spectroscopic Analysis with VIZSLA

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ABSTRACT

Supplementary Online Material

Figure S1 shows the inner structure of the ultra-high vacuum (UHV) compatible chamber of the VIZSLA experimental setup during the redeposition process.

Table S1 lists the physical properties of the deposited ices and the results of electron bombardment modeling using the CASINO program (Drouin et al. 2007).

Table S2 lists the identified molecules upon 5 keV electron bombardment in the experiments conducted on pure CH₃OH ices.

Figure S2 shows the difference spectrum of electron bombarded CH₃OH ice at 3 K, zoomed in on key spectral bands.

Figures S3 and S4 show the spectra of electron bombarded CH₃OH ice during the TPD process.

Table S3–S6 show the comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of different molecules (CO, HOCH₂CH₂OH, CH₃OCHO, and HCOOH, respectively) isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

Figure S5 shows the temporal evolution of the different bands which appeared in the Ar matrix.

Table S7 lists the identified molecules upon 5 keV electron bombardment in the experiments conducted on pure CH₃OH ices.

Figure S6 shows the difference spectrum of electron bombarded CH₃NH₂ ice at 3 K, zoomed in on key spectral bands.

Figures S7 and S8 show the spectra of electron bombarded CH₃NH₂ ice during the TPD process.

Table S8–S13 show the comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of different molecules (CH₃CHNH, NH₃, CH₂CHNH₂, CH₃CN, HCNC(H)CN, and HCN, respectively) isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

Figure S9 shows the temporal evolution of the different bands which appeared in the Ar matrix.

Table S14–S15 show the comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers of different (CH₃NHCH₂OH, and NH₂CH₂OH, respectively) ices.

Figures S10 and S11 show the spectra of electron bombarded CH₃OH:CH₃NH₂ ice during the TPD process.

Table S16 lists the new bands appeared in the IR spectra of the desorbing species of the CH₃OH:CH₃NH₂ ices as deposited in an Ar matrix.

Table S17–S19 show the comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of different molecules (CH₂NH, NH₂CH₂CH₂OH, and HNCO, respectively) isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

Figure S12 shows the temporal evolution of the different bands which appeared in the Ar matrix.

Fig. S1: The inner structure of the ultra-high vacuum (UHV) compatible chamber of the VIZSLA experimental setup during the redeposition process. Panel (a) corresponds to the structure during the redeposition–irradiation cycles, panel (b) shows the structure during the redeposition.

Table S1: The physical properties of the deposited ices and the results of electron bombardment modeling using the CASINO program (Drouin et al. 2007).

	CH ₃ OH ice	CH ₃ NH ₂ ice	CH ₃ OH:CH ₃ NH ₂ ice
density of ice (g/cm ³)	1.02±0.03 (Bouilloud et al. 2015)	0.85±0.05 (Holtom et al. 2005)	0.95
average molar mass of molecules in ice (g/mol)	32.0	31.1	31.4
irradiated area (cm ²)	0.7±0.1	0.7±0.1	0.7±0.1
initial energy of the electrons (keV)	5.00	5.00	5.00
applied electron current (nA)	100±10	100±10	100±10
irradiation time (min)	60	60	60
simulated average penetration depth (nm)	383±11	467±14	424±13
average backscattered energy of the electrons (keV)	2.75±0.08	2.74±0.08	2.76±0.08
average transmitted energy of the electrons (keV)	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00
fraction of backscattered electrons (%)	6.46±0.39	5.20±0.31	5.87±0.35
fraction of transmitted electrons (%)	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00
dose per molecule (eV)	21.1±3.1	20.2±2.9	20.1±2.9

Table S2: The identified molecules in the experiments conducted on pure CH₃OH ices.

Molecule	Electron irradiated CH ₃ OH ice			
	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)			
	This work	Bennett et al. (2007)	Jheeta et al. (2013)	Sullivan et al. (2016)
H ₂ COH	1195	1192	1345	1195
H ₂ CO	1724	1726	1724	1724
H ₂ CO	1505	1496	–	–
H ₂ CO	1249	1245	–	1250
HCO	1843	1849, 1841	–	–
CO	2134	2134	2136	2134
CH ₄	1304	1303	1304	1303
CO ₂	2340	2345	2341	2341
HOCH ₂ CH ₂ OH	1091	1090	–	1092
HOCH ₂ CH ₂ OH	–	889	–	891
HOCH ₂ CH ₂ OH	–	856	–	864
HOCH ₂ CHO	1746	1747	–	–
CH ₃ OCHO	1724	1718	–	–
CH ₃ OCHO	1160	1160	–	–
CH ₃ OCHO	920	916	–	–
CH ₃ OCH ₃	1160	–	–	1161
CH ₃ OCH ₃	1091	–	–	–
CH ₃ OCH ₃	920	–	–	914

Fig. S2: Difference spectrum of electron bombarded CH₃OH ice at 3 K, zoomed in on key spectral bands. The difference spectrum was obtained by subtracting the MIR spectrum recorded after the electron bombardment from the spectrum recorded after the deposition.

Fig. S3: Overall IR spectra recorded during the TPD of pure CH_3OH ice. The figure displays the spectra of the ice after the first cycle of deposition at 3 K (red), after the first cycle of irradiation at 3 K (blue), at the start of the TPD at 3 K (brown), at 65 K (green), at 145 K (purple), at 155 K (orange), at 175 K (grey), and at 215 K (light blue).

Fig. S4: IR spectra recorded during the TPD of pure CH_3OH ice, zoomed in on key spectral bands. The figure displays the spectra of the ice after the first cycle of deposition at 3 K (red), after the first cycle of irradiation at 3 K (blue), at the start of the TPD at 3 K (brown), at 65 K (green), at 145 K (purple), at 155 K (orange), at 175 K (grey), and at 215 K (light blue).

Table S3: Comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of CO isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

CO					
$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^a	I^a	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^b	$I^{b,c}$	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^d	$I^{c,d}$
2148.9	s	2149.8	100	2149.6	100
2138.6	s	2137.7	45	2137.2	37
2150	w	—	—	—	—

^a Dubost (1976)

^b This work, experiments with pure CH_3OH ice.

^c Relative IR intensity, normalized to the most intense band.

^d This work, experiments with $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}:\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2$ ice.

Table S4: Comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of HOCH₂CH₂OH isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

HOCH ₂ CH ₂ OH			
$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^a	<i>I</i> ^a	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^b	<i>I</i> ^{b,c}
3673.0	w	3672.2	—*
3667.0	s	—*	—*
3635.0	m	3634.8	100
3629.0	w	3632.9	100
3624.5	w	3624.4	81
3617.0	w	3618.6	—*
2968.0	m	—*	—*
2940.0	m	—*	—*
2891.0	m	—*	—*
2885.0	w	2885.4	82
1470.0	vw	—	—
1468.0	w	—	—
1461.5	w	—	—
1459.5	w	—	—
1415.5	w	—	—
1383.0	m	1383.7	14
1350.0	w	1346.7	6
1284.0	vw	1286.7	5
1271.0	m	1269.0	9
1255.0	w	—	—
1246.0	w	—	—
1239.0	w	1239.9	16
1163.0	s	1164.1	7
1160.0	m	—	—
1159.0	m	1158.6	7
1102.0	m	1103.6	—*
1100.0	s	1100.9	—*
1098.0	m	1098.2	—*
1079.5	vw	—*	—*
1073.5	m	1073.9	26
1041.5, 1038.0	vs,s	1043.7	34
880.0	m	881.6	17
865.0	m	866.0	1
863.0	m	—	—

* Overlaps.

^a Frei et al. (1977)^b This work, experiments with pure CH₃OH ice.^c Relative IR intensity, normalized to the most intense band.**Table S5:** Comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of CH₃OCHO isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

CH ₃ OCHO		
$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^a	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^b	<i>I</i> ^{b,c}
3480	—	—
3035	—	—
3014	—	—
2964.1	—*	—*
2938.5	—*	—*
2929	—*	—*
2902	—*	—*
2843.8	—	—
2119	—	—
2074	—	—
1970	—	—
1833	—	—
1778.4	1777.7	100
1747.1	1746.9	81
1745.2	—*	—*
1708.3	—	—
1460.1	—	—
1446.8	—	—
1434.7	—	—
1373.1	—	—
1239.9	1239.8	4
1228	—	—
1205.6	—	—
1162.5	1164.1	62
1158.1	1158.6	62
1147.7	—	—
921.6	924.8	4
916.4	916.6	1
905.4	—	—
767.9	—	—
767.0	—	—

* Overlaps.

^a Blom & Günthard (1981)^b This work, experiments with pure CH₃OH ice.^c Relative IR intensity, normalized to the most intense band.

Table S6: Comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of HCOOH isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

HCOOH				
$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^a	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^b	<i>I</i> ^{b,c}	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^d	<i>I</i> ^{c,d}
–	3731.4 ⁺	100	3731.3 ⁺	100
–	3639.9 ⁺	58	–*	–*
3546	3553.2	36	–*	–*
2950	–	–	–*	–*
1766	1764.9	9	1764.2	12
1379	–	–	–	–
1214	–	–	–	–
1036	–*	–*	–*	–*
1102	–*	–*	–*	–*
635	–	–	–	–
628	–	–	–	–

* Overlaps.

⁺HCOOH··H₂O complex according to George & Sander (2004).^a Reva et al. (1994)^b This work, experiments with pure CH₃OH ice.^c Relative IR intensity, normalized to the most intense band.^d This work, experiments with CH₃OH:CH₃NH₂ ice.**Fig. S5:** The temporal evolution of the different species which appeared in the Ar matrix collected in the case of CH₃OH.

Table S7: The identified molecules in the experiments conducted on pure CH_3NH_2 ices.

Molecule	Electron irradiated CH_3NH_2 ice		
	Wavenumber (cm^{-1})		
	This work	Bossa et al. (2012)	Carrascosa et al. (2021)
CH_3NH , $\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}_2\text{NH}_2$	3239	–	3450–3380
CH_3NH , $\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}_2\text{NH}_2$	1653	–	–
CH_3NH , $\dot{\text{C}}\text{H}_2\text{NH}_2$	1188	–	–
CH_2NH	3145	3144	–
CH_2NH	1636	1635	–
CH_2NH	1402	1410	–
CH_2NH	1188	1187	1119
CH_2NH	1101	–	1068
CH_4	–	–	3013
CH_4	1302	1300	1303
NH_3	–	–	3390
NH_3	1072	1075	1070
CH_3NH_3^+	–	2642	2654
CH_3NH_3^+	–	2540	2553
CH_3NH_3^+	1653	1662	–
CH_3NH_3^+	1469	1476	–
CH_3NH_3^+	1459	1457	–
CH_3NH_3^+	1013	1010	–
CN^-	2081	2080	2069
CNCN	2319	2300	–
CNCN	2060	2058	–
CNCN	971	971	–
CH_3CHNH	1680	–	1668
CH_3CHNH	1444	–	1438
$\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$	3305	–	3308
$\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$	–	–	3219
$\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$	–	–	3104
$\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$	1101	–	1095
CH_3CN	–	–	2254

Fig. S7: Overall IR spectra recorded during the TPD of pure CH_3NH_2 ice. The figure displays the spectra of the ice after the first cycle of deposition at 3 K (red), after the first cycle of irradiation at 3 K (blue), at the start of the TPD at 3 K (brown), at 90 K (green), at 100 K (purple), at 140 K (orange), at 190 K (grey), and at 210 K (light blue).

Fig. S8: IR spectra recorded during the TPD of pure CH_3NH_2 ice, zoomed in on key spectral bands. The figure displays the spectra of the ice after the first cycle of deposition at 3 K (red), after the first cycle of irradiation at 3 K (blue), at the start of the TPD at 3 K (brown), at 90 K (green), at 100 K (purple), at 140 K (orange), at 190 K (grey), and at 210 K (light blue).

Table S8: Comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of CH_3CHNH isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

CH_3CHNH					
$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^a	I^a	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^b	$I^{b,c}$	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^d	$I^{c,d}$
3264	vvw	—	—	—	—
3018	m	—	—	—	—
2990	m	—*	—*	—*	—*
2954	ms	—*	—*	—*	—*
2885	m	—	—	—*	—*
1659	sh	1661.4	9	1661.1	—*
1435	s	1441.4	18	—*	—*
1433	s	—	—	—*	—*
1398	w-m	—	—	—*	—*
1392	m	—	—	—*	—*
1365	w	1363.9	18	1364.1	11
1358	s	—	—	1356.6	1
1160	vw	—	—	—*	—*
1106	ms-s	1111.7	27	1110.4	11
1040	s	1036.4	55	1036.9	100
920	w-m	—	—	—*	—*
668	s	676.2	100	675.7	6

* Overlaps.

^a Stolkin et al. (1977)

^b This work, experiments with pure CH_3NH_2 ice.

^c Relative IR intensity, normalized to the most intense band.

^d This work, experiments with $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}:\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2$ ice.

Table S9: Comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of NH_3 isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

NH_3				
$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^a	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^b	$I^{b,c}$	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^d	$I^{c,d}$
3460	—	—	—	—
3346	—	—	—	—
1639	—	—	—	—
975	974.6	100	974.2	100

^a Bossa et al. (2008)

^b This work, experiments with pure CH_3NH_2 ice.

^c Relative IR intensity, normalized to the most intense band.

^d This work, experiments with $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}:\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2$ ice.

Table S10: Comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of CH_2CHNH_2 in gas phase and isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

CH_2CHNH_2				
Gas phase		Ar matrix		
$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^a	$I^{a,b}$	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^c	$I^{b,c}$	
2987, 2976	8	—*	—*	
1672, 1668	52	1661.4	6	
1625	13	—*	—*	
1454	0.6	1455.4	6	
1260, 1248	17	—	—	
1084, 1078	3	1075.7	18	
1046, 1039	6	1036.4	35	
812, 805	49	808.9	100	
684, 616	100	676.2	65	

* Overlaps.

^a Hamada et al. (1984)

^b Relative IR intensity, normalized to the most intense band.

^c This work, experiments with pure CH_3NH_2 ice.

Table S11: Comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of CH_3CN isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

CH_3CN		
$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^a	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^b	$I^{b,c}$
3004	—	—
2950.3	—*	—*
2258.4	—	—
1445	1441.4	33
1408.0	—	—
1375.8	—	—
1037.9	1036.4	100
916.9	916.4	40

* Overlaps.

^a Freedman & Nixon (1972)

^b This work, experiments with pure CH_3NH_2 ice.

^c Relative IR intensity, normalized to the most intense band.

Table S12: Comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of HCNC(H)CN isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

HCNC(H)CN					
$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^a	<i>I</i> ^a	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^b	<i>I</i> ^{b,c}	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^d	<i>I</i> ^{c,d}
2216.1	w	–	–	–	–
1980.9, 1973.2	s	–	–	–	–
848.8	w	–	–	–	–
730.7, 713.2	vs	729.1, 712.0	100	729.3, 712.4	100

^a Maier & Endres (2000)^b This work, experiments with pure CH₃NH₂ ice.^c Relative IR intensity, normalized to the most intense band.^d This work, experiments with CH₃OH:CH₃NH₂ ice.**Table S13:** Comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of HCN isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

HCN				
$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^a	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^b	<i>I</i> ^{b,c}	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^d	<i>I</i> ^{c,d}
3303.3	3306.3	93	–*	–*
2093.4	–	–	–	–
720.2	720.8	100	720.9	100

* Overlaps.

^a King & Nixon (1968)^b This work, experiments with pure CH₃NH₂ ice.^c Relative IR intensity, normalized to the most intense band.^d This work, experiments with CH₃OH:CH₃NH₂ ice.**Table S14:** Comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers of CH₃NHCH₂OH ices.

CH ₃ NHCH ₂ OH	
$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^a	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^b
3260	–*
3072	–*
2981	–*
2949	2955
2888	2878
2868	–*
1490	1499
1475	–*
1455	–*
1445	–*
1414	–*
1376	1381
1305	1302
1225	–
1146	1140
1120	1124
1063	1064
1031	1035
1009	–*
870	–*

* Overlaps.

^a Vinogradoff et al. (2013)^b This work, experiments with CH₃OH:CH₃NH₂ ice.**Fig. S9:** The temporal evolution of the different species which appeared in the Ar matrix collected in the case of CH₃NH₂.**Table S15:** Comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers of NH₂CH₂OH ices.

NH ₂ CH ₂ OH	
$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^a	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^b
3333	–*
3207	–*
3040	–*
2942	2955
2893	2881
1657, 1611	1680
1481, 1466	1499
1392	–*
1235	1249
1096, 1040	1096
1012, 997	–*
951	–*
871, 838	–*

* Overlaps.

^a Bossa et al. (2009)^b This work, experiments with CH₃OH:CH₃NH₂ ice.

Fig. S10: Overall IR spectra recorded during the TPD of $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}:\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2$ ice. The figure displays the spectra of the ice after the first cycle of deposition at 3 K (red), after the first cycle of irradiation at 3 K (blue), at the start of the TPD at 3 K (brown), at 115 K (green), at 140 K (purple), at 150 K (orange), and at 190 K (grey).

Fig. S11: IR spectra recorded during the TPD of $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}:\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2$ ice, zoomed in on key spectral bands. The figure displays the spectra of the ice after the first cycle of deposition at 3 K (red), after the first cycle of irradiation at 3 K (blue), at the start of the TPD at 3 K (brown), at 115 K (green), at 140 K (purple), at 150 K (orange), and at 190 K (grey).

Table S16: List of the new bands that appeared in the IR spectra of the desorbing species of the $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}:\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2$ ices as deposited in an Ar matrix. The species were accumulated in the Ar matrix between 175 K and 300 K.

$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1})	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1})	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1})
3731.3	1646.6	1090.2
3723.7	1602.3	1075.7
3666.3	1599.6	1060.6
3653.8	1593.6	1056.3
3650.1	1474.6	1044.7
3615.0	1454.3	1036.9
3555.0	1447.9	1025.2
3548.2	1390.6	990.6
3541.2	1364.1	974.2
3533.9	1356.6	965.0
3527.2	1342.2	959.8
3455.9	1293.0	774.9
3005.4	1268.8	772.0
2847.7	1231.9	738.2
2259.7	1197.1	729.3
2149.6	1185.6	720.9
2137.2	1135.7	712.4
2101.7	1124.9	697.5
2055.0	1110.4	675.7
1764.3	1100.0	

Table S17: Comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of CH_2NH isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

CH_2NH		
$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^a	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^b	$I^{b,c}$
3036	—*	—*
2924	—*	—*
1640	1646.6	3
1453	1454.3	14
1347	1342.2	0.4
1059	1060.6, 1056.3	100

* Overlaps.

^a Jacox & Milligan (1975)

^b This work, experiments with $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}:\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2$ ice.

^c Relative IR intensity, normalized to the most intense band.

Table S18: Comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of $\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

$\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$			
$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^a	$I^{a,b}$	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) ^c	$I^{b,c}$
3666	m	3666.3	100
3662	m	—*	—*
3646	m	—*	—*
3561	sh	—	—
3555	m	3555.0	10
3548	m	3548.2	11
3534	sh	3533.9	5

* Overlaps.

^a Räsänen et al. (1982)

^b Relative IR intensity, normalized to the most intense band.

^c This work, experiments with $\text{CH}_3\text{OH}:\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2$ ice.

Table S19: Comparison of experimental vibrational wavenumbers and IR intensities of HNCO isolated in a solid Ar matrix.

HNCO			
$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^a	<i>I</i> ^{a,b}	$\tilde{\nu}$ (cm ⁻¹) ^c	<i>I</i> ^{b,c}
3516.8	13	—*	—*
3505.7	13	—*	—*
2259.0	100	2259.7	100
1315.0	7	—	—
769.8	16	—*	—*

* Overlaps.

^a Teles et al. (1989)^b Relative IR intensity, normalized to the most intense band.^c This work, experiments with CH₃OH:CH₃NH₂ ice.**Fig. S12:** The temporal evolution of the different species which appeared in the Ar matrix collected in the case of CH₃OH:CH₃NH₂.

References

- Bennett, C. J., Chen, S.-H., Sun, B.-J., Chang, A. H. H., & Kaiser, R. I. 2007, *ApJ*, 660, 1588
- Blom, C. E. & Günthard, H. H. 1981, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 84, 267
- Bossa, J.-B., Borget, F., Duvernay, F., et al. 2012, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 65, 129
- Bossa, J.-B., Duvernay, F., Theulé, P., Borget, F., & Chiavassa, T. 2008, *Chem. Phys.*, 354, 211
- Bossa, J. B., Theule, P., Duvernay, F., & Chiavassa, T. 2009, *ApJ*, 707, 1524
- Bouilloud, M., Fray, N., Bénilan, Y., et al. 2015, *MNRAS*, 451, 2145
- Carrascosa, H., González Díaz, C., Muñoz Caro, G. M., Gómez, P. C., & Sanz, M. L. 2021, *MNRAS*, 506, 791
- Drouin, D., Couture, A. R., Joly, D., et al. 2007, *Scanning*, 29, 92
- Dubost, H. 1976, *Chem. Phys.*, 12, 139
- Freedman, T. B. & Nixon, E. R. 1972, *Spectrochim. Acta Part A: Mol. Spectrosc.*, 28, 1375
- Frei, H., Ha, T.-K., Meyer, R., & Günthard, H. H. 1977, *Chem. Phys.*, 25, 271
- George, L. & Sander, W. 2004, *Spectrochim. Acta Part A: Mol. Biomol. Spectrosc.*, 60, 3225
- Hamada, Y., Hashiguchi, K., Tsuboi, M., Koga, Y., & Kondo, S. 1984, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, 105, 93
- Holtom, P. D., Bennett, C. J., Osamura, Y., Mason, N. J., & Kaiser, R. I. 2005, *ApJ*, 626, 940
- Jacox, M. E. & Milligan, D. E. 1975, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, 56, 333
- Jheeta, S., Domaracka, A., Ptasinska, S., Sivaraman, B., & Mason, N. J. 2013, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 556, 359
- King, C. M. & Nixon, E. R. 1968, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 48, 1685
- Maier, G. & Endres, J. 2000, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2000, 2535
- Räsänen, M., Aspiala, A., Homanen, L., & Murto, J. 1982, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 96, 81
- Reva, I., Plokhotnichenko, A. M., Radchenko, E. D., Sheina, G. G., & Blagoi, Y. P. 1994, *Spectrochim. Acta Part A: Mol. Spectrosc.*, 50, 1107
- Stolkin, I., Ha, T.-K., & Günthard, H. H. 1977, *Chem. Phys.*, 21, 327
- Sullivan, K. K., Boamah, M. D., Shulenberger, K. E., et al. 2016, *MNRAS*, 460, 664
- Teles, J. H., Maier, G., Hess Jr, A. B., et al. 1989, *Chem. Ber.*, 122, 753
- Vinogradoff, V., Duvernay, F., Danger, G., et al. 2013, *A&A*, 549, A40